

Electrochemical investigations and analysis of allethrin in formulations and in household dust

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Allethrin, an effective synthetic pyrethroid against various pests is studied by employing the electrochemical techniques such as direct current polarography (DCP), cyclic voltammetry (CV), differential pulse polarography (DPP), controlled potential electrolysis (CPE) and millicoulometry (MC). The compound is electrochemically reducible over the pH range 2.0–12.0. It is found to undergo single step irreversible, diffusion controlled and pH dependent reduction.

Allethrin [2-methyl-4-oxo-3-(2-propenyl)-2-cyclopenten-1-yl-2,2-dimethyl-3-(2-methyl-1-propenyl)cyclopropane carboxylate¹ is a synthetic pyrethroid insecticide for the control of various pests. Allethrin is used almost exclusively in homes and gardens for control flies, crawling insects, bed bugs, cockroaches and mosquitoes². It is widely used in Textile fabrics industry³.

Allethrin is non-phytotoxic, but it is toxic to insects as natural pyrethrins, but it has longer residual effects⁴. Allethrin is toxic to birds (LD_{50} 17.5 mg/dm⁻³), fishes (LD_{50} 30.1 mg/dm⁻³), male and female rats is (1100 and 685 mg kg⁻¹, respectively), 370 mg kg⁻¹ in mice and 4 290 mg kg⁻¹ in rabbits⁵.

Studies have been carried out on allethrin by different techniques in various samples⁶. Previous studies have shown that allethrin can be reduced electrochemically⁷. The electrochemical reduction of allethrin in non-aqueous solvents was studied by Coomber *et al.*⁸.

Results and discussion

Allethrin exhibits only one polarographic wave/peak throughout the pH range 2.0 to 12.0 (Fig. 1). This wave/peak is due to the reduction of carbon at the double bond in a two-electron process to a saturated product⁹. In the present study, no reduction response was obtained for keto group in acetone at the pH range 2.0–12.0.

Controlled potential electrolysis was performed at –0.85 V to carryout the isolation of reduction product of allethrin at mercury electrode surface at pH 4.0. The product was identified as saturated product and the same was confirmed from IR spectral studies (absence of peak in the range 3650–3300 cm⁻¹).

Fig. 1. Typical differential pulse polarogram of allethrin (pH 4.0, concn. : 0.5 mM, drop time = 2 s, pulse amplitude 50 mV).

Table 1. Typical kinetic data of allethrin

pH of the supporting electrolyte	DCP		CV		DPP	
	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d µA	$-E_p$ V	i_p µA	$-E_m$ V	i_m µA
2.0	0.66	0.6	0.69	3.8	0.68	0.42
4.0	0.87	0.8	0.90	4.3	0.88	0.70
6.0	1.00	0.7	1.01	3.4	1.01	0.68

Millicoulometry was employed to find out the number of electrons involved in the electrode process, using the method of Devries and Kroon¹⁰. The results showed the number of electrons involved in reduction of allethrin to be two.

Table 2. DPP determination of allethrin in formulations

Allethrin formulations	Labelled amount (mg)	i_m (μA)	Average amount found \pm S.D.(mg)	Average recovery (%)
Hit (aerosol spray)	0.25	0.451	0.233 \pm 0.01	93.20
Baygon (aerosol spray)	0.5	0.890	0.459 \pm 0.05	91.80
Jet				
(a) Coil	0.1	0.182	0.094 \pm 0.02	94.00
(b) Mat	0.5	0.899	0.462 \pm 0.05	92.80

*Averaged results for three determinations.

Typical kinetic parameters of the electrode process evaluated from different techniques are reported in Table 1. The reason for slight decrease in diffusion coefficient (D) values with increase in pH may be due to the less availability of protons with increase in pH. The observed rate constant values in acidic media are high indicating that the rate of the reaction in acidic media is fast due to proton involvement.

On the basis of the experimental results obtained from different techniques, the following reduction mechanism is presented for allethrin.

where Ar =

Recovery experiments :

In the present study the best dpp peak obtained at pH 4.0 with a drop time of 2 s, a pulse amplitude of 50 mV, and an applied potential (peak potential) of -0.91 V was utilized for the recovery experiments of allethrin. Quantitative measurements were successful in the concentration range of 1.0×10^{-4} to 2.5 ppb with the lower detection limit of 2.1 ppb.

(i) Allethrin formulations :

DPP under the experimental conditions mentioned above was used to determine allethrin in various formulations. For the analysis of allethrin in formulations, the widely used formulations in India such as jet coil, mat, Baygon (microspray) and Hit (aerosol spray) were chosen. Following the procedures specified in the experimental section, the final concentration of allethrin in the analytical solution was $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$. Assay results for allethrin in formulations are given in Table 2.

(ii) Household dust samples :

We have selected three different house hold dust samples for applying the DPP method. The dust samples were drawn 7, 14, 21 days gap from three houses to study the carry-over of the residues. Results obtained for the determination of allethrin in dust samples are presented in Table 3.

Experimental

Substances and solutions :

Allethrin (95%) was obtained from aero industries, Gujarat and it was used without further purification. Universal buffer solutions ranging from pH 2.0 to 12.0 were prepared using 0.2 M boric acid, 0.05 M citric acid and 0.1 M trisodium orthophosphate¹¹.

Experimental techniques and instrumentation :

A detailed description of the instrumentation and experimental conditions has been reported earlier¹². All the experiments were performed at 25^o. pH measurements were carried out with an Elico digital pH meter.

(i) Allethrin formulations :

The required quantity of allethrin formulation corresponding to a $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ stock solution was accurately measured and transferred into a 50 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol. A solution of approximately $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ was prepared by dilution of this stock solution with supporting electrolyte and the solution was de-oxygenated with N₂ gas for 10 min. After the polarogram was recorded, small increments (0.2 ml) of standard solution were added and a polarogram was recorded after each addition under similar experimental conditions.

Table 3. Analysis of allethrin in household dust samples by DPP

Compd.	Dosage (g)	Sampling interval (days)	Average amount Found \pm S.D. (mg)			Average recovery (%)		
			Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3
Allethrin	10.00	7	0.05 \pm 0.01	0.09 \pm 0.04	0.04 \pm 0.03	89.23	88.91	83.30
		14	1.02 \pm 0.03	1.11 \pm 0.01	1.00 \pm 0.02	94.32	91.15	90.40
		21	4.93 \pm 0.02	5.04 \pm 0.03	4.81 \pm 0.01	97.90	99.00	96.89

*Averaged results for three determinations.

(ii) Household dust samples :

Inspection of sites and collection of dust/material samples for analysis of allethrin was performed on request. For the detection of elevated concentrations of allethrin, we took 10 g of dust from three different houses. The extracts were prepared by the treatment of acetone. Then the extract was evaporated to dryness. The residue of allethrin was dissolved in methanol and determined by DPP method.

Conclusion :

As can be seen from the data in Tables 2 and 3, the recovery ranges for allethrin in formulations and household dust are 91.80–94.00% and 83.30–99.00% respectively. The proposed DPP method is very simple, fast, fairly sensitive and sufficiently accurate, precise and better suited than conventional methods like spectrophotometry or chromatography to characterize the electrochemical mechanistic and analytical investigation of allethrin. All these features make DPP an attractive analytical approach for analysis of pyrethroid class of compounds containing >C=C< moiety.

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